

SILICON CARBIDE FIBERS DERIVED FROM CHLORINE CONTAINING POLYSILANES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel type of SiC fiber manufacture corresponding to the polymer route. New developed chlorine containing polysilanes are used to spin green fibers. Those fibers are cured under ammonia and temperature treatment to become infusible. After a pyrolysis step around 1000°C amorphous silicon carbide fibers are obtained. The structure change from polysilane into silicon carbide is observed by IR- and NMR- spectroscopy and by x-ray diffraction of the pyrolysed fibers. The fibers possess a good thermal stability up to at least 1500°C. Further properties like tensile strength and morphology are investigated too.

INTRODUCTION

Since Yajima and coworkers established the polymeric route for SiC fiber manufacture [1] such fibers have been under research. The advantage of this polymeric route is the spinnability of the polymeric precursor at relatively low temperatures and a subsequent conversion of the polymer into ceramic material like silicon carbide or silicon nitride. A drawback of such fibers is the instable chemical composition which includes high amounts of oxygen in general cases. This is the main reason why the application temperature of the NICALON or TYRANNO fibers are limited to about 1000°C. Some effort was done to solve this problem by Takeda et al. [2] Toreki et al. [3] and Mocaer et al. [4] recently. They used electron beam curing, solution spinning or γ -radiation curing to avoid an introduction of oxygen during the fiber manufacture. However, the production of fibers became much more expensive compared with the conventional process.

We used a new reactive polysilane as ceramic precursor. This polysilane was spinnable and the curing process can be performed as chemical crosslinking by introduction of NH groups derived from added ammonia [5, 6]. The pyrolysis process is similar to the Yajima process but the resulting fibers show a very low oxygen content and a mixed silicon - carbon - nitrogen structure as it will be shown in this paper.

Figure 1: used manufacture process

MANUFACTURE OF FIBERS

The chlorine containing polysilanes were synthesized by a catalytic redistribution what is described in detail elsewhere [7]. This polysilane was molten and spun with a spinneret in a laboratory scale. Afterwards the as spun polymer fibers were put in a vessel for crosslinking with ammonia. This vessel was heated up to temperatures of 215°C and streamed by argon / ammonia mixtures to set up a crosslinking reaction of the polymer fibers (reaction scheme (1), (2)).

After performing the curing (crosslinking) process the fibers were introduced into a tube furnace and heated to various temperatures in the range between 800 and 1600°C. The received ceramic fibers were investigated with regard to their structure and their properties. The principal scheme of the manufacture is shown in figure 1 and described in more details in [8].

The advantage of the developed process bases on the reactivity (Si-Cl-bonds) of the polysilanes used for spinning. This reactivity enables to do the curing with ammonia and avoids the introduction of oxygen.

The structural change caused by the crosslinking of the polysilane with amine groups was investigated by means of IR- and NMR- spectroscopy. Some results of these measurements were already published in [6]. Further research was done and the crosslinking process can be described finally as an introduction of NH-groups into the polysilane skeleton. This reaction occurs with an additional formation of ammonium chloride (1), (2). Furthermore the IR-spectra show Si-N bands (around 900 cm^{-1}) in addition to the original existent Si-C bands. The amount of the Si-N groups in relation to the Si-C groups is increasing with the curing temperature.

The ^{29}Si -NMR spectra of those samples completely agree with the results which were found by the IR-investigations. In figure 2 the spectra show the formation of a variety of different $\text{SiC}_x\text{N}_{1-x}$ groups which are presented by the peaks in the wide range between -20 and -50 ppm. This range should be assigned to $\text{SiC}_x\text{N}_{1-x}$ groups with respect to Lippowitz et al. [9]. That an increasing curing temperature goes with an increasing amount of formed Si-N bonds is also obvious by the NMR-spectra. A rapid acceleration of the crosslinking reaction which is accompanied by the formation of Si-N bonds was observed at temperatures higher than 170°C .

STRUCTURE OF PYROLYSED CURED POLYSILANES

The alteration of cured and pyrolysed polysilanes in comparison with only pyrolysed polysilanes was investigated by IR- and NMR-spectroscopy and x-ray diffraction. Figure 3 shows the ratio of Si-N and Si-C vibrations derived from the IR-spectra of samples pyrolysed at 1200°C and cured at various temperatures under ammonia / argon mixtures. Additionally ^{29}Si -NMR spectra are shown in figure 4. Both methods show that Si-N bonds exist in the cured samples whereas exclusive Si-C structures exist in the not cured sample. As it was expected the amount of the Si-

N bonds is increased by higher curing temperatures. The curing process with ammonia obviously creates a Si-C-N structure similar to that found by Mocaer et al. [4] where a polysilazane was pyrolysed. Figure 5 shows the intensities of the signals which are attributed to SiCN groups. With regard to the results of the investigated cured samples one could conclude that the actual fibers should possess a polycarbosilane like structure with Si-N bonds included. This structure converts during the pyrolysis into a carbo nitride state.

The x-ray patterns which are shown in figure 6 give evidence that the original obtained nanocrystallites of β -SiC of the pyrolysed uncured sample do not exist any more after a curing treatment of the fibers. Even at low curing temperatures of 150°C no real x-ray peak is obtained after pyrolysis. The structure seems to be completely amorphous up to temperatures of about 1300°C. The mixed Si-C-N groups do not crystallize at these temperatures probably caused by a high activation energy which is necessary to cause a grain growth of SiC or Si_3N_4 after formation of more or less stable nuclei. The nucleation temperature of this material should be attributed to

Figure 3: Si-N and Si-C vibrations of cured polysilane samples after pyrolysis at 1200°C in IR-spectra

a temperature range between 1100 and 1150°C as it was found by thermoanalysis.

The patterns in figure 7 show the crystallization of those samples with respect to the pyrolysis temperature. A very broad peak is observed after a treatment at 1300°C. The x-ray peak which concerns the (111) peak of the β -SiC sharpens with increasing temperature. Some α -SiC peaks can be observed at temperatures higher than 1500°C but the crystallites keep in a size less than few nanometers.

These x-ray results are in agreement with the results of the NMR-spectroscopy where a peak sharpening was observed with increasing temperature and more defined near range groups occur. Surprisingly no crystalline Si_3N_4 was found. The crystallization of nitride is obviously inhibited and the nitrogen is completely involved in the amorphous parts of the material.

SOME PROPERTIES OF THE OBTAINED FIBERS

The fibers obtained from the described and investigated process were tested with regard to thermal behavior and mechanical properties. These tests are still in progress and with respect to some optimization of the processing there should be expected a significant improvement

First of all the chlorine and oxygen content of the obtained silicon carbide fibers were analyzed.

The introduction of oxygen can be avoided by strict handling under dry inert conditions up to the pyrolysis step (oxygen content 0.9 %, chlorine content 1.4 %). The chlorine which is contained in the as synthesized polysilane is mostly removed during the curing and pyrolysis. But it is included in the fiber at a certain level even at high temperatures of more than 1500°C as it was found in powder samples. The effect of this impurity could be a stabilization of the amorphous or of the nanocrystalline structure. If the chlorine remains in the fiber it would be a desired behavior.

Thermal analysis shows that the fiber is stable in air up to at least 1500°C (max. testing temperature). Figure 8 shows that almost no mass loss occurs up to this temperature. This is a favorable behavior especially in comparison to the NICALON fibers. The little mass loss of

about 2 % which occurs at a temperature of 400°C should be attributed to a burn out of free

Figure 5: intensity of SiCN groups in ^{29}Si -NMR spectra derived from peak deconvolution

carbon. But this little amount would not influence the further properties dramatically.

The analysis of the free carbon amount is in agreement with the result of the thermoanalysis. There were less than 2 mass % of free carbon found in samples after a pyrolysis at 1200°C. This carbon is attributed to the glassy like state which was shown by RAMAN-spectroscopy.

SEM investigations show that a lot of faults like cracks and slopes exist in the prepared fibers. These faults mainly result from the discontinuous pyrolysis process which is changed into an continuous process in the near future. Those faults will surely cause a degraded mechanical strength as it was found by the tensile test described in the following part.

As it could be expected from the SEM investigations the most of the fiber samples were very heavily damaged and degraded with regard to the tensile strength. This results in low values and a wide variation of the measurements. The range of the measured tensile strength reaches from 50 MPa up to 1000 MPa. The majority of the samples shows a tensile strength around 300 MPa. The Young module could only be estimated to about 150 GPa at this time. The wide range and the variation encourages that a more sophisticated equipment will strongly improve the mechanical properties so that the actual values should be regarded similar to that of NICALON. Additionally the mechanical properties should stay stable up to temperatures of at least 1500°C because no chemical change was observed and even the crystallite growth is not very significant up to this temperature.

Figure 6: x-ray patterns of polysilane pyrolysed at 1200°C in relation to the curing regime

SUMMARY

The described process and the structural investigations of the obtained fibers show that thermal stable and relatively cheap silicon carbide fibers can be produced from chlorine containing polysilanes. By use of a crosslinking step including ammonia and thermal treatment the introduction of oxygen can be almost completely avoided.

The fibers probably change their structure from a polysilane into a mixed polysilane/carbosilane/silazane structure in the surface regions. This mixed polymer is transformed into a stable amorphous Si-C-N network what starts to crystallize at temperatures higher than 1300°C. The crystallographic phase is β -silicon carbide with low contents of α -silicon carbide at higher temperatures than 1500°C. The crystallite size is kept under a limit of 10 nm probably caused by chlorine impurities which still remain in the samples up to temperatures as high as 1800°C.

The thermal stability of the fibers under air is outstanding compared with other materials like NICALON.

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